

Studies on the Reaction of Salicylimine with Dioxouranium (UO_2^{2+}) and Correlation of IR and TGA Data with the U-O Bond Length

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A number of trisalicylimino-uranylates with metallic, organic and complex cations have been prepared. Their general compositions are $M^I [\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{NO})_3]$ where $M^I = \text{K}^+, \text{Cs}^+, \text{Tl}^+, \text{NH}_4^+, \text{Ph}_4\text{As}^+$, pyridinium ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_6\text{N}^+$), quinolinium ($\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{N}^+$), oxinium ($\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{NO}^+$), $\text{cis-}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}_2]^+$, $\text{trans-}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}_2]^+$ cations and $M^{II} [\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{NO})_3]_2$ where $M^{II} = \text{Ca}^{2+}, \text{Sr}^{2+}, \text{Ba}^{2+}, \text{Zn}^{2+}$ etc. From IR spectra of these complexes, the asymmetric stretching frequency ($\bar{\nu}_3$ in cm^{-1}) values of the UO_2^{2+} -entity indicate the following decreasing order of stability of the complexes and the increasing order of $\bar{\nu}_3$ values.

$\text{Cs}^+ > \text{cis-}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}_2]^+ > \text{Ba}^{2+} > \text{Tl}^+ =$

$\text{trans-}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}_2]^+ > \text{Ph}_4\text{As}^+ = \text{NH}_4^+ > \text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{OXH}^+ > \text{PyH}^+$

Thermogravimetric analyses of these compounds also indicate the same decreasing order of stability with the exception of the complex cationic compounds for which an explanation has been provided by the authors. So there is a direct parallelism between thermal stability and stability indicated by $\bar{\nu}_3$ values from IR spectra. From the observed asymmetric stretching frequency ($\bar{\nu}_3$ in cm^{-1}) of the UO_2^{2+} entity, the force constant, F_{UO} in $\text{mdynes}/\text{\AA}$ and the bond length R_{UO} in \AA of 'U-O' bond have been calculated. Plot of decomposition temperature (T°) vs $\bar{\nu}_3$ is a straight line and these two parameters are inversely related.

Electronic spectra of some of these compounds have also been measured. All these data indicate linearity of the UO_2^{2+} -entity and a chain structure for the trisalicylimino-uranylates.

SALICYLIMINE was used earlier to prepare 1:2 complexes of copper and nickel. The thermal stability of the resultant complexes permitted gravimetric estimation of copper and nickel respectively¹. The present authors used salicylimine to prepare 1:3 complexes of dioxouranium (VI). In strongly ammoniacal medium uranyl ion reacts with excess salicylimine to produce $\text{NH}_4[\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{NO})_3]$ where $\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{NO} =$ anion of salicylimine. Various salts of trisalicylimino-uranylate anion with metallic, organic and complex cations have been prepared from $\text{NH}_4[\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{NO})_3]$ by metathesis reaction in the pH range 5.5-6.5 in methanol-acetone (1:1) medium. Their colors are listed in Table 1. These salts are soluble in dimethyl formamide (DMF) and dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO). With the exception of the metallic salts, the ammonium and the organo-cationic compounds are soluble in acetone-methanol mixture (1:1). But all are insoluble in CS_2 , C_6H_6 , cyclohexane and kerosene. It was observed during the preparation of metallic derivatives by metathesis, if slight-excess of acetone-methanol solvent mixture was added and heated, the precipitate of the metallic derivative dissolved immediately; however the precipitate reappeared partly (50-60%) on cooling. This fact prevents the gravimetric estimation of these

metallic ions, although the metallic trisalicylimino-uranylates are granular substances, insoluble in water, thermally stable having definite composition and suitable for direct weighing. These metallic derivatives on being dried over concentrated H_2SO_4 , become sparingly soluble in organic solvents.

Experimental

All reagents used were of AnalaR grade. Salicylimine was prepared as described in the literature¹.

Analysis:

Uranium was analysed after decomposing the sample with concentrated H_2SO_4 followed by H_2O_2 and then reducing U(VI) to U(IV) by the Jones reductor and titrating back to the U(VI) state with standard $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$. Nitrogen was estimated by the micro-Dumas method. Water of crystallisation was calculated from loss of weight upto 110° from TGA data.

Preparation of Ammonium trisalicylimino-uranylate:

8 grams of salicylaldehyde was dissolved in a mixture

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containing 80 ml liquor NH_3 and 720 ml water; the yellow precipitate that appeared was dissolved by warming and 1.6 grams of uranyl nitrate was added. The solution was warmed at $50^\circ - 55^\circ$ for about 5 minutes. The deep red solution was allowed to stand for about one hour when red granular crystals gradually separated. It was filtered, washed with water and dried over concentrated H_2SO_4 . The yield was only 1.4 grams. The NH_4^+ -salt was purified by crystallisation from acetone-methanol (1:1) mixture.

Preparation of $M^I [\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{NO})_3]$ where $M^I = \text{K}^+, \text{Cs}^+, \text{Tl}^+, \text{Ph}_4\text{As}^+, \text{cis- and trans-}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}_2]^+$ and $M^{II} [\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{NO})_3]_2$ where $M^{II} = \text{Ca}^{2+}, \text{Sr}^{2+}, \text{Ba}^{2+}$ and Zn^{2+} by metathesis :

These compounds were prepared by mixing 150 ml of 0.7% solution of soluble salts (chloride, nitrate or sulphate) of the respective metal with 80 ml of 1.25% solution of $\text{NH}_4[\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{NO})_3]$ in acetone-methanol (1:1) mixture; the solution was stirred well and the precipitate was allowed to settle, filtered, washed with water, then with acetone-methanol mixture and dried over concentrated H_2SO_4 . The yields are about 50%.

For the preparation of the Zn^{2+} -salt, 200 ml of 0.5% ZnSO_4 solution was used, other factors remaining unchanged. In all these cases pH of the mixture was maintained between 5.5 to 6.5.

Preparation of $M^I [\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{NO})_3]$ where $M^I = \text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{NO}^+, \text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}^+, \text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}^+$ by metathesis :

Pyridinium and quinolinium hydrochlorides were prepared by suspending about 1.5 ml of pyridine or quinoline in 10ml water and then lowering the pH to about 5.5 by adding dilute HCl. Oxinium cation was prepared by dissolving about 1 gram oxine in requisite amount of ethyl alcohol and the pH was lowered to 5.5 by adding dilute HCl. The resulting hydrochloride solutions were mixed with 80 ml of 1.25% solution of $\text{NH}_4[\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{NO})_3]$ in acetone-methanol (1:1) mixture; then water was gradually added to the solution to complete the precipitation of the organo-cationic derivative. The precipitates were filtered, washed and dried as before.

Physico-chemical measurements :

Thermogravimetric analyses were carried out in a manual recording thermobalance of local make using a heating rate of $7^\circ/\text{min}$. Results are tabulated in Tables 2 and 4 respectively. IR-spectra were recorded in Beckman IR 20 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. Some of the characteristic IR-absorption bands (in cm^{-1}) have been mentioned in the text; $\bar{\nu}_3$ (in cm^{-1}) values of the UO_2^{2+} -entity in different compounds are given in Table 2. Electronic spectra were recorded by a Hilger UVISPEK spectrophotometer in Dimethyl formamide solvent. Spectral data together with band assignments are shown in Table 3, but the data for the cobalt complexes in methanol-water solvent have been taken from a standard literature².

Results and Discussion

Of the fourteen compounds listed in Table 1, nine are hydrated and the rest five are anhydrous. The presence of water molecules in these nine hydrated samples is also indicated by O-H stretching vibrations around 3400 cm^{-1} . TGA data showed that the hydrated compounds begin to lose weight (water) from about $40^\circ - 60^\circ$ and they become anhydrous at about 110° . Decomposition temperatures (T° indicating stability order) of these anhydrous compounds are listed in Table 2. All these compounds lose weight rapidly from about 290° to around 400° due to decomposition of organic mater. The residues are metallic diuranates in the case of metallic trisallylimino-uranylates and U_8O_8 in the case of ammonium and organocationic compounds. The behaviour of the complex cationic compounds is interesting. According to Duval³, cis- $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and trans- $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ show the loss of weight from 85° and 45° respectively. The cis and trans- $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}_2][\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{O}_6\text{NO})_3]$ compounds begin to lose weight at 90° and 50° respectively and reach first constant level at 120° and 100° respectively. The present authors believe that the complex cationic parts are responsible for the first decomposition since these complex cationic compounds contain no water (as indicated by IR spectra) and Duval's data³ also support this view. The second decomposition due to anionic parts, starts at 150° and 130° respectively. The data are listed in Table 4.

The band assignments of the IR data were made consulting standard literature⁴⁻⁹. In all the hydrated compounds except for the NH_4^+ -salt there is a broad band around 3400 cm^{-1} corresponding to the H-bonded O-H stretching vibration in water of crystallisation and shoulders at 3260 cm^{-1} and 3200 cm^{-1} corresponding to N-H stretching vibrations of the imino-group ($-\text{CH}=\text{NH}$). However, in the NH_4^+ -compound the shoulder at 3200 cm^{-1} changes to a broad band due to N-H stretching vibrations of the NH_4^+ -group. In all these compounds both the aromatic aldimine frequency of the type $\text{Ar}-\text{CH}=\text{NH}$ and the O-disubstituted ring vibration appear as strong bands in the regions $1585-1630 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $730-760 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The C-O stretching vibration in chelate rings as well as the skeletal bending mode appear as bands of varying intensity in the regions $1140-1170 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $900-915 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively.

In all these compounds $\bar{\nu}_3$ -the asymmetric stretching frequency of the UO_2^{2+} entity is observed in the region $855-905 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 2), depending on the nature of the cation outside the coordination sphere. A weak band, observed in all these compounds in the region $1110-1130 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, is assignable to the combination frequency ($\bar{\nu}_2 + \bar{\nu}_3$) of the UO_2^{2+} -entity. The absence of a strong vibration assignable to $\bar{\nu}_1$ implies linearity for the UO_2^{2+} -entity ($D \propto h$)^{10,11,12}.

From IR-spectra, the observed asymmetric stretching frequency ($\bar{\nu}_3$ in cm^{-1}) values of the UO_2^{2+} -entity have been used to calculate the force constant (F_{UO}) in millidynes per angstrom (mdynes/ \AA) by the McGlynn method¹⁵ and these F_{UO} -values on substitution in the

TABLE 1

Name	Colour	Sl. No.	% of Uranium		% of nitrogen		% of H ₂ O loss upto 110°	
			Calculated	Found	Calculated	Found	Calculated	Found
K [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · 4H ₂ O	brick-red	1	32.12	32.33	5.667	5.01	9.705	9.804
Cs [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · 3H ₂ O	orange-red	2	29.14	28.87	5.14	4.9	6.61	6.029
Ca [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · 7H ₂ O	orange	3	33.37	33.26	5.888	5.21	8.835	9.173
Sr [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · 6H ₂ O	orange-red	4	32.72	33.21	5.775	5.12	7.423	7.59
Ba [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · 6H ₂ O	red	5	31.63	32.05	5.582	5.02	7.176	7.297
Zn [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · 6H ₂ O	orange	6	33.22	32.89	5.862	5.36	7.365	7.64
Tl [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · 2H ₂ O	orange-red	7	27.35	27.6	4.826	4.16	4.137	3.78
NH ₄ [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · H ₂ O	dull-red	8	35.75	35.68	8.409	8.15	2.703	2.65
Ph ₄ As [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · 3H ₂ O	deep yellow	9	22.13	21.87	3.941	3.53	5.066	4.964
OXH [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂]	orange-red	10	30.67	30.2	7.216	6.96	—	—
C ₈ H ₈ N [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂]	orange	11	33.52	33.36	7.886	7.48	—	—
C ₉ H ₈ N [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂]	orange-yellow	12	31.32	30.95	7.369	6.91	—	—
cis-[Co(en) ₂ Cl ₂] [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂]	chocolate brown	13	27.05	26.94	11.14	10.56	—	—
Trans-[Co(en) ₂ Cl ₂] [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂]	dark-orange	14	27.05	26.98	11.14	10.71	—	—

For the complex cationic derivatives satisfactory cobalt analysis have been found.

Abbreviations : Ph₄As⁺=tetraphenyl arsonium cation, OX=Oxine, en=ethylene diamine.

TABLE 2

Compound	$\bar{\nu}_3$ (in cm ⁻¹) of the UO ₂ ²⁺ -entity	Force constant F _{UO} in mdynes/A of the 'U-O' bond calculated from the $\bar{\nu}_3$ value	Bond length R _{UO} in Å of the 'U-O' bond calculated from $\bar{\nu}_3$ value	Temperature (°C) at which the anhydrous compound begins to lose weight T°C
Cs [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · 3H ₂ O	855	6.078	1.7619	170
Ba [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · 6H ₂ O	870	6.292	1.7551	144
Tl [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · 2H ₂ O	875	6.365	1.7528	130
cis-[Co(en) ₂ Cl ₂] [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂]	865	6.220	1.7572	90*
Trans-[Co(en) ₂ Cl ₂] [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂]	875	6.365	1.7528	50*
Ph ₄ As [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · 3H ₂ O	880	6.439	1.7505	120
NH ₄ [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · H ₂ O	880	6.439	1.7505	120
Zn [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · 6H ₂ O	885	6.510	1.7484	110
OXH [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂]	890	6.586	1.7462	100*
PyH [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂]	905	6.808	1.7399	70*

* These compounds possess no water of crystallisation.

Abbreviations : Py=pyridine, Ph₄As⁺=tetraphenyl arsonium cation.
en=ethylene diammine, OX=Oxine.

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA IN DIMETHYL FORMAMIDE

Compound	λ_{max} (m μ)	$\bar{\nu}$ cm ⁻¹	log ϵ	Assignment
K [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · 4H ₂ O	398	25,130	3.6699	$1\Sigma_g^+ \rightarrow 3\pi_u$
Cs [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · 3H ₂ O	399	25,060	3.5600	$1\Sigma_g^+ \rightarrow 3\pi_u$
Ba [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · 6H ₂ O	396	25,260	3.7949	$1\Sigma_g^+ \rightarrow 3\pi_u$
Zn [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · 6H ₂ O	395	25,310	3.8167	$1\Sigma_g^+ \rightarrow 3\pi_u$
Tl [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂] · 2H ₂ O	397	25,190	3.5237	$1\Sigma_g^+ \rightarrow 3\pi_u$
NH ₄ [(UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂)] ₂ H ₂ O	400	25,000	3.6317	$1\Sigma_g^+ \rightarrow 3\pi_u$
cis-[Co(en) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl*	240	41,670	4.28	
	390	25,630	1.89	
Trans-[Co(en) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl*	252	39,680	4.31	
	385	25,970	1.64	
cis-[Co(en) ₂ Cl ₂] [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂]	386	25,900	3.6083	$1\Sigma_g^+ \rightarrow 3\pi_u$
	570	17,540	2.5400	$1A_{1g} \rightarrow 1T_{1g}$
	700	14,290	2.3207	$1A_{1g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}$
Trans-[Co(en) ₂ Cl ₂] [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂]	372	26,880	3.6950	$1\Sigma_g^+ \rightarrow 3\pi_u$
	388	25,770	3.7071	$1A_{1g} \rightarrow 1T_{2g}$
	695	14,390	2.1340	$1A_{1g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}$

* Data supplied by F. Basolo, J. A. C. S., 1950, 27, 4393.
Abbreviation : en=ethylene diamine.

TABLE 4

Compound	Loss of weight starts at (°C)	First constant weight level reached at (°C)	Loss of weight upto first constant weight level (in percentage)	Decomposition of the anionic part starts at (°C)
cis-[Co(en) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl · H ₂ O*	85	—	—	—
trans-[Co(en) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl*	45	—	—	150
cis-[Co(en) ₂ Cl ₂] [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂]	90	120	3.529	130
trans-[Co(en)Cl ₂] [UO ₂ (C ₇ H ₆ NO) ₂]	50	100	3.477	—

* Data supplied by Duval*.

Jones' equation, $R_{UO} = F_{UO}^{-1/3} + d$, yield the 'U-O' bond lengths (R_{UO}) in angstrom unit (\AA)¹³. The data are listed in Table 2. Use of Bullock's method^{19,26} indicates that for the nitrate-complexes¹⁹, F_{UO} and R_{UO} -values are improved by only 1-3% and 0.1-0.3% respectively as compared to McGlynn's method. So following McGlynn's method (using $\bar{\nu}_3$ -only), the theoretically calculated R_{UO} -values are in the range 1.7399 \AA to 1.7619 \AA and they are well in the range (1.69-1.76 \AA) found from crystallographic measurements on various uranyl complexes^{21,22,23,24,25}.

The data in Table 2 have been utilised to plot F_{UO} (mdynes/ \AA) vs R_{UO} (\AA), decomposition temperature (T°) vs $\bar{\nu}_3$ (cm^{-1}) and decomposition temperature (T°) vs R_{UO} (\AA). They are shown in figure 1. The plot of F_{UO} vs R_{UO} is an asymptote as expected¹⁴, so also that of T° vs R_{UO} (appears to be a straight line over a small range of variation). The plot of T° vs $\bar{\nu}_3$ (cm^{-1}) is a straight line with the exception of the complex cationic compounds and these two parameters are inversely related. For the complex cationic derivatives, if we consider the decomposition temperatures of the anionic parts from Table 4, instead of the decomposition temperatures(T°) of the anhydrous compounds from Table 2. then these two points are also included in the linear plot of (T°) vs $\bar{\nu}_3$ (cm^{-1}). It is evident

from Table 2 that the $\bar{\nu}_3$ -values decrease in the following order :

According to McGlynn, Smith and Neely¹⁵, the series indicates the stability of the complexes in the reverse order. So the data in Tables 2 and 4 indicate a parallelism between thermal stability and stability indicated by $\bar{\nu}_3$ -values from IR-spectra; the $\bar{\nu}_3$ -values essentially indicate the stability of the anionic parts of the complex uranylates.

In order to explain the insolubility of the trisalicylimino-uranylates in organic solvents after drying and also to explain the stability order in Tables 2 and 4, the present authors suggest the linearity of the UO_2^{2+} -entity and a chain structure for these complexes; this chain structure is similar to that for $\text{H}[\text{UO}_2(\text{OX})_3]$ as suggested by Bullwinkel and Noble¹⁶

in which the various cations take the place of the acidic hydrogen atoms in the compounds under discus-

Fig. 1. Plots of (—○—○—) F_{UO} (mdynes/ \AA) vs R_{UO} (\AA) of the 'U-O' bond ;
 (—□—□—) decomposition temperature (T°) vs $\bar{\nu}_3$ (cm^{-1}) of the 'U-O' bond ;
 (—△—△—) decomposition temperature (T°) vs R_{UO} (\AA) of the 'U-O' bond.

sion. Evidently there will be elongation of the axial 'U-O' bond of the UO_2^{2+} -entity through ionic interactions¹⁸ between the cations (e.g., Cs^+ , Tl^+ etc.) and the axial oxygens, thereby somewhat lowering the electrostatic repulsion¹⁵ of the highly negative axial oxygens with the piled up charge on the equatorially ligated uranium atom in the anionic complex; hexagonal equatorial ligation of the free UO_2^{2+} -entity (D_{3h}) results in piling up of charge on the uranium atom¹⁵. The cis-complex cation, having a higher dipole moment than the trans-one, leads to greater ionic interactions with the axial oxygens, resulting in greater 'U-O' bond elongation and higher stability (Table 4). Thus it may be concluded that the longer the 'U-O' bond length through ionic interactions with cations of increasing electropositive character, the smaller is the $\bar{\nu}_3$ (cm^{-1}) value and the higher is the thermal stability of that particular complex uranyl.

In the low-energy absorption spectra (18,000-27,770 cm^{-1}) of all the complexes under discussion, which is a $S \rightarrow T$ electron transfer process within the UO_2^{2+} -ion¹¹, it appears that the middle component ($^3\pi_u$) of the transition $^1\Sigma_g^+ \rightarrow ^3\pi_u$ is observed in each case (Table 3). For the complex cationic compounds two additional bands appear (Table 3) and these data are consistent with the spectra of spinpaired octahedral d^6 -Co(III)^{2,17,18,20} type. These data indicate that the octahedral geometry of the d^6 -Co(III) complex cations remains unchanged in the complex uranylates under discussion.

Correlations of IR and TGA data with 'U-O' bond length for a series of other uranyl complexes (1:3) are now being established and the results will be communicated shortly.

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